

ISic0469

Dedication to Apollo

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2017-07-21

Last Change

2019-03-08 - Jonathan Prag edited and added imagery after preparation of new edition for Prag and Tigano 2017

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Said to come from Halaesa

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 3573

Physical Description

A rectangular block of limestone

Dimensions

Height 26 cm

Width 91 cm

Depth 15 cm

Layout

The text occupies two lines with interpuncts visible at the end of line 1 and between words in line 2. It is possible that the text continued below, or to the right, on another block, but it is complete in itself

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are archaic in form, in particular the square, open P; the form of the R; the off-vertical N, and the rigid S.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 70-120 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Apoline
2. L(ucius) · Carnius · C(ai) · f(ilius)

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Lucius Carnius, son of Gaius (dedicated this) to Apollo

Translation (en)

Lucius Carnius, figlio di Gaius (ha dedicato questo) ad Apollo

Commentary

The dative Apoline (rather than Apollini) is well attested in archaic Latin (Sihler 1995: 284, §276.5; e.g. CIL 12, nos.384, 399, 1928, 2233). If the inscription is genuinely from Halaesa, then it is further evidence for the importance of the sanctuary of Apollo in the city (Diod. Sic. 14.16.4; cf. IG 14, no.352, col. II, ll. 52-54 (= ISic1174 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1174>]); SEG 59 no.1100; Prestianni Giallombardo 2003: 1075-1081). The inscription also provides some of the earliest evidence for Roman presence on the island (cf. Facella 2006: 203-204), although the name Carnius is not otherwise attested on the island. Together with the milestone of Aurelius Cotta from Corleone (ILLRP 1274 = ISic0610 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0610>] , c.252 BC), and the Egadi rostra inscriptions (Prag 2014, before 241 BC, e.g. ISic4367 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4367>]), this is one of the earliest Latin inscriptions from Sicily.

The form Apoline and the letter forms suggest a date in the third or early second century BC.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491767

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